

SPECIFIC FEATURES OF METHYLENE BLUE IN THE OXIDATION KINETICS OF MODEL SUBSTRATES IN ACIDIC MEDIUM

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ABSTRACT

Methylene blue, a thiazine dye, used as a model oxidant to probe the electron transfer reactions involved in mitochondria. It has also been used as a key component of a wide range of optical oxygen sensors used in the food industry for food packaging under a modified atmosphere of nitrogen or carbon dioxide (map). The prophylactic preoperative methylene blue administration increases the fractional oxygen saturation with a consequent increase of the safety margin against perioperative hypoxemia by decreasing the methemoglobin level in a patient with congenital methemoglobinemia. Degradation of methylene blue by gold nanoparticles highlights its medicinal importance in a completely different manner. Wide range of redox potential plays a significant role in this regard. Recent studies indicate the presence of nanoparticles in the model systems in which methylene blue acts as an oxidant.

Keywords: methylene blue, redox potential , nanoparticles

INTRODUCTION

Methylene blue (tetramethylthionine chloride, $C_{16}H_{18}ClN_3S$) is a heterocyclic

aromatic thiazine dye. It occurs as odorless dark blue crystals and is soluble in water but only sparingly so in alcohol. In its oxidized

state, the color of MB is blue due to the fact that the phenothiazinium molecule absorbs visible light strongly in the region of 600–700 nm, thus allowing the remainder of the visible spectrum (350–600 nm) to be transmitted. It has numerous uses in various field of science such as: in chemistry [1-4], biology [5-7], industries [8] and medicine [6,9]. Methylene blue is easily reduced by various reducing agents to the colourless hydrogenated molecule, leucomethylene blue (LMB), which can be oxidized back to the blue colour. In its reduced form (leucoMB), it is colorless and does not absorb light in the visible region [10]. LeucoMB is uncharged, lipophilic, and enters cells by diffusion across the plasma membrane where it can be re-oxidized and thus sequestered within the cells[11]. Oxidized MB and leucoMB together form a reversible oxidation-reduction system or electron donor-acceptor couple. These processes have found application in numerous inventions like data recording holographic industries, optical data storage, food and pharmaceutical industries. Such reduction is also used in checking the purity of milk [12,13]. The redox-indicator

properties of this couple have been used extensively in the quantitative analysis of a large number of reducing agents, such as glucose and ascorbic acid. In clinics, the redox properties of MB have been utilized in treatments of methemoglobinemias and ifosfamide-induced encephalopathy. MB is the first-line treatment for congenital, occupational, and drug induced methemoglobinemias. MB acts as an electron donor in the non-enzymatic reduction of methemoglobin. An NADPH methemoglobin reductase, catalyses the reduction of MB to leuco-MB. This reaction transfers electrons to methemoglobin non-enzymatically, restoring functional hemoglobin and MB. Recent results indicate that methylene blue or its derivatives could (1) have an additional effect against Alzheimer Disease by inhibiting brain caspase activity, (2) be used as a drug to prevent caspase activation in other conditions, and (3) predispose chronically treated individuals to cancer via the inhibition of caspases [14]. MB was the first synthetic compound ever used as an antiseptic in clinical therapy and the first antiseptic dye to be used therapeutically. In

fact, the use of MB and its derivatives was widespread before the advent of sulfonamides and penicillin in chemotherapy. MB has also been a lead compound in drug research against various bacterial and viral infections not to mention its part in the development of the phenothiazine neuroleptic family over the years, MB has also been used in human and veterinary medicine for a number of therapeutic and diagnostic procedures including use as a stain in neuroanatomy and bacteriology, as a redox coloring agent in biochemical studies, as a targeting agent for various types of cancer such as melanoma and lung cancer, and as an antiseptic compound. One of the most common clinical applications is for treating methemoglobinemia, either inborn or induced by overexposure to drugs, to industrial chemicals such as nitrophenols, or to environmental poisons such as excessive nitrate in well water or cyanide compounds. Presently, MB is used clinically in a wide range of indications, such as methemoglobinemia, ifosfamide-induced encephalopathy and thyroid surgery. In June 2009, 14 clinical trials are registered in the United States to investigate the clinical

utility of MB in areas ranging from anesthesiology to treatments of depression and psychosis.

Photochemical reactions, particularly those involving photoinduced electron transfer processes, establish a substantial contribution to the modern synthetic chemistry, and the polymer community has been increasingly interested in exploiting and developing novel photochemical strategies. These reactions are efficiently utilized in almost every aspect of macromolecular architecture synthesis, involving initiation, control of the reaction kinetics and molecular structures, functionalization, and decoration, etc. Merging with polymerization techniques, photochemistry has opened up new intriguing and powerful avenues for macromolecular synthesis. Construction of various polymers with incredibly complex structures and specific control over the chain topology, as well as providing the opportunity to manipulate the reaction course through spatiotemporal control, are one of the unique abilities of such photochemical reactions [14].

In the catalytic action of metal ions, MB plays a very vital role. In such systems, the addition of a redox inactive metal ion considerably alters the rate of reaction. This effect is termed as cooperativity effect. In biological systems, the redox active metal centre is often associated with another metal centre that can accelerate the redox process of O₂ in these reactions. Further, the improved NO conversion into N₂ by synergetic effect over a H-ZSM-5/V₂O₅ hybrid catalyst has also been reported. An important example of such a cooperativity effect has been noticed in the function of proteins where amino acid H-63, H-71, H-80 and ASP-83 are bound to Zn (II) whereas H-63 also coordinates with Cu (II). Due to this, Zn (II) accelerates copper substrate interactions and contributes to the protein's stability. It has been observed in our laboratories that the catalytic activities of Ru(III) is appreciably enhanced by trace amounts of Cu(II) [2.0 x 10⁻⁸ M] [15].

The metal ions such as Cu(II), Zn(II), Co(II), Ru(III) will be used as catalysts and the influence exerted by the neighbouring group will be studied to get information about intramolecular effects. Recently, the

binding of cysteine and glutathione to Ru(II) and Ru(III) centers has been studied kinetically and the product reactivities have been compared [16]. In our laboratories, it is found that the energetics of Ru catalysed oxidation of cysteine is more favourable as compared to Ru catalysed oxidation of glutathione under similar conditions [17]. It indicates that the glutamyl moiety may hamper the activity of functional cysteinyl group in GSH. This suggests the possibility of intramolecular effects and in the proposed project, this aspect of metal ion catalysis will be studied in detail. Incidentally, in enzyme kinetics, T C Bruice has reported intramolecular catalysis.

Transition metal ions are effective catalysts of redox processes and their interaction with biomolecules are not spin restricted. The reactivity of sulphur centre depends on the environment, its oxidation state and the presence of specific metal ion and in the free form as S²⁻ and RS⁻, the oxidation of sulphur is highly complex. Our investigations have revealed that the metal-substrate interactions in some cases are the time dependent and secondly, the effect of dissolved oxygen appreciably depends on

the metal ion as well as on the nature of the substrate. This aspect of metal ion catalysis in the oxidation of sulphhydryl substrates with biologically important electron receptor methylene blue is investigated in the laboratory[17].

Conclusion:

It appears that many of the biological effects of MB are closely associated with its unique physicochemical properties, including its redox characteristics, ionic charges, and light spectrum characteristics. MB has a high solubility in aqueous media; preclinical and clinical studies demonstrate a low toxicity profile. In addition, its ability to permeate cellular membranes and to cross the blood-brain barrier makes MB attractive as a potential therapeutic agent. Formation of nanoparticles with in the reaction system containing methylene blue open questions regarding the effect of MB in such systems and thus further studies are needed

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